

Project Report (short version, translated from Norwegian):

Langsrud, S, Heir, E., Møretrø, T., Røssvoll, E, Hansen, A.A:

Mapping of practices that affect the occurrence of Listeria in Norwegian salmon products. (2010). Nofima.

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Tilgjengelighet: Fortrolig	Dato: 26.03.2010
Tittel: Kartlegging av bedriftspraksis (produkt, prosess og organisering) som hemmer og fremmer forekomst av Listeria i norske lakseprodukter	Prosjektnummer: O3935
Formål med prosjektet:	
Oppdragsgiver: Norske Sjømatbedrifters Landsforening	Oppdragsgivers ref:
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Summary

This is a translation of parts of a Norwegian project report published in 2010 that can be found at [Kartlegging av bedriftspraksis som hemmer og fremmer forekomst av Listeria i norske lakseprodukter: Forprosjekt \(fhf.no\)](#). The project was funded by the Norwegian Seafood Research Fund (FHF). Kristin Lauritzsen was the administrative project manager. The responsible R&D institution was Nofima Mat AS, represented by Solveig Langsrud.

The aim of the project was to map the situation in the salmon industry regarding areas of improvement to avoid *Listeria monocytogenes* (Listeria) in Norwegian salmon, prepare proposals for further work to improve the situation and spread knowledge about Listeria problems to the salmon industry. A review of literature in the area, a web-based mapping of the situation on the control of Listeria in salmon companies, company visits and dialogue with relevant actors were conducted. This translated version is a short version of the mapping part of the project.

The web-based survey was fully or partially answered by 52 companies and completely completed by 38 companies. The survey showed very large variations between different salmon companies in terms of occurrence of Listeria, equipment park, monitoring and routines to avoid Listeria in products. For example, 9% of companies took daily samples for Listeria in the production environment and 9% never took this type of sample, some companies flushed floors during production daily while others reported that this never occurred. Furthermore, there were large differences in zoning between individual establishments. There were no systematic differences between different types of companies (size, type of production) with regard to routines of importance for combating Listeria, with some exceptions (e.g. monitoring, which was often more extensive for larger companies). All the companies that carried out sampling when Listeria was found in raw materials or products, and 92 % implemented measures when found in the environment. The companies had good knowledge of which measures are relevant for Listeria problems.

Approach

A web based survey on practices to monitor and combat listeria was sent to NSL and FHL members in the autumn of 2009. The responses from the survey were anonymous. Data from the survey were analysed and a report (PP presentation) was made.

Results

Respondents

The survey was fully or partially answered by 52 companies and completely completed by 38 companies. The non-response rate was evenly distributed between different types of enterprises (size, raw materials, products) and data from all responses were therefore used in the analyses.

The number of full-time equivalents was <10 in 22% of the companies that responded to the survey 10-50 in 35% and > 50 in 43% of the companies. 60% of the largest companies had two or three shifts, compared to 6 and 11% of the small and medium-sized companies, respectively.

In total, 57% of the companies in the survey had live salmon as their main raw material, 26% had gutted salmon and 17% filleted salmon. 65% of the large companies started with live fish and 31% started with gutted salmon. For the medium-sized and small companies, about 30% started with live, gutted and filleted salmon, respectively. 57% had an external supplier of raw materials, 30% an internal supplier and 13% both an external and internal supplier. The large enterprises more often had both external and internal suppliers of raw materials than the small and medium-sized enterprises.

The main end product was gutted salmon for 33% of the companies, filleted salmon for 31% and smoked salmon for 30%. The majority of the large companies in the survey were slaughterhouses that had filleted (44%) and gutted (36%) fish as their main end product. Half of the small and medium-sized enterprises produced smoked or heat-treated products.

Three salmon companies were visited. The first company was a slaughterhouse that produced gutted salmon from live salmon. The company had two production shifts and one shift for cleaning over 50 employees and internal suppliers of raw materials. The other company produced frozen salmon fillets from gutted salmon. The company had two shifts, over 50 employees and 2-5 raw material suppliers. The last company produced smoked salmon from gutted salmon. The company had between 10.15 full-time equivalents, one shift and 2-5 external raw material suppliers.

Raw material control

Samples of raw materials were taken by 90% of the companies and 69% stated that they have a sampling plan for *Listeria* on raw materials. Five companies, three small and two large, neither took samples themselves nor received test results from suppliers. All types of raw materials were represented among these five. 67% of the companies took raw material samples themselves, 6% received test results from suppliers and 18% both took samples themselves and received results from suppliers. About 90% of large and medium-sized companies took *Listeria* samples of the raw materials themselves and 56% of the small ones.

Table 1 shows how often raw materials were tested for *Listeria* among the companies in the survey.

Table 1 Frequency of *Listeria* Samples of Raw Materials

	%
Every day	33
2-5 times a week	9
1 time per week	26
2-3 times per month	12
1 time per month	7
Less than 1 time per month	14

For the companies that had live and gutted salmon as raw material, 89% took from one or more of the three relevant areas; gills, fish skin and belly. Over 50% of the companies took *Listeria* samples from all three areas gills, fish skin and abdomen. Three companies did not take *Listeria* samples from these points and one stated ice as a sampling site. Most used swabs to take the sample (73%), followed by chiffonette (24%) and meat sampling (12%).

Of the 9 companies that had filleted salmon as a raw material, 1 company did not take *Listeria* samples of the raw material. Of the remaining 8 companies, 2 took from the fillet surface (swab), 2 took a depth sample, while 4 did not know where the sample was taken from. Product samples were taken in the same way as raw material samples.

41% of the companies stated that they have never detected *Listeria* in the raw materials, 47% in 1-5% of the samples and 9% in 6-10% of the samples. One company reported a frequency of *Listeria* in raw materials of 11-25%. This was a large company that processes live salmon from more than 10 raw material suppliers. This company had a sampling plan, took the raw material samples themselves from gills, fish skin and belly once a week. Companies that had fewer raw material suppliers generally had fewer discoveries of *Listeria*: 50-70% of those who had 1-5 suppliers never detect *Listeria*, compared to 12-16% of those who had more than 5 suppliers.

Only 8% of the companies stated that they use some form of surface treatment on salmon. Two companies stated that they use desliming.

91% stated that they initiated measures every time *Listeria* was detected in the raw materials and 9% if this was found repeatedly. Table 2 shows the measures taken in the event of detection.

Table 2 Measures after the detection of Listeria in raw materials

	%
Washing down exposed equipment	52
Intensifies product control	50
Intensifies environmental control	47
Washing down the entire facility	47
Intensifying raw material control	38
Withdrawing/withholding product	26
Other, comment	18
Ships to specific customers	15
No action	3

Monitoring of Listeria in a production environment

94% (48 of 51) had a sampling plan for the production environment. All the largest companies stated that they had a sampling plan, compared to 88% of the medium-sized and 78% of the small. 2 companies only had a sampling plan for the end product and 2 only had for the production environment.

9% of the companies took samples for listeria daily, 31% weekly and 42% monthly. Only large companies took daily Listeria samples in the production environment (17%). 25% of large companies took weekly, 42% monthly, 4% semi-annual, 4% annual and 8% never took Listeria samples. Table 3 shows the frequency of positive listeria samples production environment for all the establishments and by different types of departments.

Table 3 Frequency of detection of Listeria in production environment after cleaning

% proportion of samples positive for Listeria	All companies (%)	Gutting/fillet (%)	Smoking/heat treatment (%)
0 %	38	30	50
1-5 %	43	43	43
6-10 %	14	17	7
>11 %	6	8	0

Table 4 shows the percentage of the companies that took samples at various points (given that they had this equipment in the production line) and the percentage that stated that they had detected Listeria (of those that took samples from this point). It is important to note that it was

only stated whether *Listeria* had been found at this point and not the frequency of findings. The table is ranked according to the proportion of establishments that took samples in this section.

For points in contact with the product and where there is the greatest risk of infection with *Listeria*, the bacterium had been detected by most factories on conveyor belts (55%), trimming tables (28%) and slicers (28%). All the companies that had the equipment took samples at these points. For points that are not in direct contact with the product, *Listeria* had been detected in drains (62%), followed by floors (38%) and vacuum equipment (32%). The companies were encouraged to indicate points where *Listeria* had been detected, but which were not stated in the list. *Listeria* had been detected on buttons/panels on the machine, floor mats, collection machine and gutter, box washer and in gutting machine.

Table 4 Sampling sites for *Listeria* and percent of establishments that have detected *Listeria* in the respective points.

	% taking samples	% positive samples
Conveyor belt	100	55
Trimming table	100	28
Slicing machine	100	28
Drains	94	62
Bone remover	89	24
Filleting Machine	89	21
Condensation surfaces	86	27
Portion cutter	86	17
Knives	82	7
Floor	81	38
Vacuum Equipment	73	32
Injection needles	73	13
Walls	69	8
Gloves	69	17
Washing equipment	63	5
Aprons	59	10
Wheels	53	16
Tools	43	0

79% stated that they initiated measures every time Listeria was detected in the final product and 13% if this was found repeatedly.

Table 5 Measures taken when Listeria is found in a production environment

	%
Washing down equipment related to Listeria findings	71
Intensify environmental control	71
Washing down the entire facility	60
Replacing parts of equipment with Listeria	29
Change cleaning procedure	29
Other, comment	14
No action	6

Cleaning program and routines aimed at combating listeria

52% of the slaughterhouses stated that they never use fish that had been in contact with the floor in further processing. 16% used this fish for alternative treatment (e.g. products that were to be heat treated). 32% always or occasionally used fish that had been in contact with the floor, and most rinsed the salmon with clean water before using it.

36% stated that some equipment was difficult to keep clean. Examples of equipment/areas were vacuum systems, conveyor belts, electrical components/motors, inside tanks, gutting machines, grading machines, filleting machines, roofs and drains. 82% replaced parts in case of wear/tear, 48% if they were difficult to clean, 61% according to the maintenance plan and 29% in the case of Listeria findings. An example of a part that was replaced in Listeria discoveries was conveyor belts. 90% of the companies stated that equipment was always washed after repairs.

80% of the companies stated that they agreed with the statement that "when purchasing equipment, we focus on making it easy to clean". 5% completely disagreed with this statement. 70% of the companies agreed with the statement that "when purchasing equipment, we focus on making it easy to disassemble" and 5% disagreed. 40% of the companies were concerned that the equipment dried quickly. Companies that had one shift were more concerned with drying equipment than those that had several shifts.

Condensation dripping on the production line was the biggest problem in slaughterhouses and fillet production. 25% and 43% of these companies, respectively, had detected Listeria in condensate water.

Small and medium-sized enterprises mostly had their own cleaners (100 and 70% respectively), while among the large enterprises about half (46%) had external cleaners. No correlation was established between Listeria occurrence and the use of external or in-house cleaners.

40% of slaughter companies dismantled equipment daily and 70% of other processing factories. The equipment was completely dismantled at least weekly in most companies.

72% of the slaughterhouses stated that they had identified points in the facility that were cleaned extra well. Equipment that was mentioned in this context were gutting machines, vacuum suction, drains and conveyors. 61% of the filleting plants mentioned machines, conveyor belts, knives, contact surfaces, loose equipment, injecting machine and vacuum system as areas that were washed particularly well. For the smokehouses, 47% stated slicing machines, slicing knives, smoke carts, floors, drains, contact surfaces, boxes, smoke grates and smoking cabinets as critical points. 33% of the smokehouses stated that they had points that were washed extra well (slicing knife, contact surfaces).

All the companies stated that detergents were used for industrial cleaning, and 10-20% of the departments had automatic washing of conveyor belts and other equipment. This was most common in slaughterhouses (24%) and filleting departments (16%). About 90% of the companies used chemical disinfection and 4-7% used heat disinfection. Around 30% stated using fogging disinfection, a few use UV and one company ozone.

Experiences with listeria prevention and elimination

The companies gave the following reasons for Listeria problems (the number of companies with similar/same answers is given):

With Listeria problems, I think it is most often caused by:

- Contaminated raw materials (11)
- Poor cleaning (9)
- Equipment that is difficult to clean, Listeria in niches in the equipment (8)
 - Vacuum suction, gutting machines, confined spaces, drains
- Poor zoning (3)
- Poor drying (2)
- Too high a temperature in the premises for a period of time (2)

The companies were also asked what measures, in their own experience, should be taken to combat Listeria.

In our experience, Listeria problems are best solved by:

1. Cleaning and routines aimed at Listeria

- Preventive, good cleaning and good hygiene (13)
- Full washdown in case of problem (8)
- Cleaning of special areas in case of problems (4)
- Dismantling before washing (4)
- Using equipment with hygienic design (2)
- Drying after washing
- Using your own cleaners
- Prevent unauthorized access

2. Competence and training

- Training, competence, attitudes (6)

3. Production Environment Monitoring

- Environmental Monitoring (3)

4. Raw materials

- Focus on raw materials
- Follow-up of suppliers